

Task-Based Learning Strategy and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Reading Comprehension in Obio/Akpor L.G.A. Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated task-based learning strategy and senior secondary school students' academic performance in reading comprehension in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study. The quasi-experimental design was employed. The population of the study consisted of ten thousand and eleven (10,011) students from senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. A sample of four hundred (400) students was used. One (1) public and one (1) private senior secondary school were drawn for the study through simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was structured questions tagged: "English Language Performance Reading Comprehension Test (ELPRCT)." The research instrument was constructed by the researcher and validated by two experts, one in English Language and Communication Art Department and another in the Department of Curriculum Studies and Instructional Technology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Face and content validity was employed to check the validity of the instrument. Test retest was used to test the reliability coefficient and 0.78 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while t-test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that: there is significant difference in the post-test scores of task-based strategy and control group. Therefore, the treatment of task-based learning strategy at a post-test stage showed a greater effect than the pre-test. It was concluded that task-based learning strategy serves as encouragement for academic accomplishment. It was recommended that reading comprehension should be introduced using the task-based learning strategy in the teaching of reading comprehension in senior secondary schools.

Keywords: Task-based, strategy, academic, performance, secondary, school, students.

INTRODUCTION

One of the tasks that confront teachers of English language at the secondary school level is how to employ the right technique in teaching learners of different age and level, the skills to read comprehension. The reason being that the learners might have been unlucky to be deficiently taught reading comprehension in earlier classes. Students require excellent reading skill to enable them attain understanding and learn new information. A large number of learners are unable to do so because most teachers still emphasize teacher-centredness, teacher-discussion instruction, which involves text explanation, vocabulary illustration, grammar instruction and intensive drills on language form (Jin & Cortazzi, 2004).

Reading comprehension is the ability to read text, process it and recognise its meaning. This recognition comes from the communication between words that are written and how they generate knowledge outside the text/message. Comprehension involves creating meaning that is sensible and precise by linking what has been read to what the reader previously knows and thinks about all of the information until it is understood. Comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading instruction. It is therefore pertinent that reading must be accompanied with understanding else nothing has been achieved.

Reading removes educational barriers, allowing more opportunities in education by promoting language development, intellectual training and enhancing the possibility of adjustment to one's personal situation. Education is basically anchored on developing a good reading habit which is result oriented. Fayose in Simisaye and Quadri (2010) extensively discussed the paramount role reading plays in students' educational pursuit and agreed that it promotes a deep awareness and builds the child up emotionally and intellectually. Hence, reading is a very important issue which is not about enjoyment but a necessity; the basic tool in education. Reading is therefore, a highly valuable skill and activity. Improvement in reading skills will reduce unnecessary reading time and enable students read in more focused and selective manner. It will also increase the level of understanding and concentration.

The paradigm shift from conventional teaching to student-centred teaching has led to innovations in teacher-centred. Teaching is now characterised by the use of clear, measurable goals and students' outcomes, and direct involvement of learners in activities that produce deeper understanding of the content through the development of skills that are readily transferable to work and life. These innovations encourage active learning, cooperation among students, prompt and appropriate feedback on performance of the students, effective time management and diversity of ways of learning. Today, students need to understand the current state of their knowledge, build on it, improve on it and make decisions in the face of uncertainty (Scott, 2015). One way these can be achieved is via the appropriate teaching and learning of the reading skill.

The classroom is made up of varying levels of proficiency in multiple reading skills, and individuals' access to background knowledge is vast and immeasurable. Meeting the reading needs of diverse learners is often cited as one of the most challenging tasks for teachers and parents (Scott, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Thus results released by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) board in 2019 showed that 1,593,442 candidates who sat for the examinations, 616,370 candidates representing 38.68% had distinction and credits (Vanguard, 2019). Students have reading problems which Davoudi and Yousefi (2015) opined that causes of reading problems for many learners include environmental, instructional, and biological sources. The environmental circumstances influence the learners' reading comprehension. Reading difficulties are the most frequent learning problems among students and the main reason for academic failure. They may have many difficulties in understanding reading materials in a disorganized environment, however, those in a peaceful and controlled environment may have more effective reading ability. Students in an insecure domicile environment find it difficult to concentrate on their reading unlike the students who find themselves in safe environments where efficiency in their reading comprehension tends to improve. There is every tendency for learners to lose focus in reading comprehension in a noisy place such as areas with volume of televisions or radios.

Regrettably, learners mostly avoid reading as they struggle to read. Thus students' poor performance in NECO and WAEC in English Language is attributed to poor reading ability as they have difficulty reading and or expressing their thoughts and ideas. This becomes a problem carried over to the graduate level, that some find it difficult to read and write letters of application to prospective organizations for jobs and even when invited for an interview, cannot express themselves fluently. It is against this backdrop that the

researcher decided to carry out this study to investigate task-based learning strategy on the performance of secondary school students in reading comprehension in Obio/Akpor L.G.A.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine task-based learning strategy and students' academic performance in reading comprehension in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. compare the pretest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method.
2. examine the posttest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference in the pretest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S?
2. What is the difference in the pretest posttest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

- H0₁: There is no significant difference in the pretest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S.
- H0₂: There is no significant difference in the pretest posttest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S.

Literature Review

Reading/Reading Comprehension

Reading is the act of looking at symbols, understanding the particular symbols, and being able to interpret the symbols (Korubo-Solomon, 2008). Reading is defined as a means of deriving meaning (reading comprehension and/or constructing meaning) or a means of communication; a means of sharing information, etc. (Wikipedia, 2008). Ituen (2014) defines reading as the course of getting information from print, i.e. information stored in written materials (books, newspapers, magazines, etc.). Also, Azikiwe (2007) defines reading as a set of distinct skills which include eye movement, speech, comprehension and vocabulary. From the fore-going definitions, reading is the ability to translate written words into meaningful language, being able to arrive at the pronunciation of a printed word. If the reader is unable to attach meaning to the word, then he or she has not read the word, since reading must end in meaning construction. Reading which is

regarded as a multifaceted cognitive process of decoding symbols in order to build or gain meaning has a means of language attainment, communication and sharing of information and ideas.

Reading is the skill of absorbing information by decoding written or printed symbols. It can take many forms including reading Mathematical and Musical Symbols - but is most commonly acquired as the skill of interpreting written symbols representing the sounds, words and sentences of the language. Reading has been recognized as part of language and so, reading is a learned skill. Learning to read is a complex task. The reader has to learn to perceive and interpret accurately, all the various symbols and symbol-patterns that are involved in written language, and to build-in the necessary skills, so that they function automatically, permitting rapid absorption of sense from the printed word (Anyanwu, 2002).

Reading is the ability to understand and correctly interpret written symbols, words and expressions. Effective reading requires literacy skills because the message is presented in symbolic and alphabetic forms. To read these forms means to understand and decode the meanings embedded in them. The acquisition and use of reading skills is a life-long exercise and since modern culture is a literate culture, there is need to sharpen these skills (Tam-George, 2002).

Reading comprehension on the other hand, is the capability to read text, process it and recognise its meaning. This recognition comes from the communication between words that are written and how they generate knowledge outside the text/message. Comprehension involves creating meaning that is sensible and precise by linking what has been read to what the reader previously knows and thinks about all of the information until it is understood. Comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading instruction. Based on the foregoing, it can be deduced that reading must be accompanied with understanding else nothing has been achieved.

Task-based Strategy

Task is a piece of work undertaken for one's self or for others, freely or for some reward (Long, in Tekena, 2014). The basic aim of second language teaching using task-based strategy is to enable learners to use the target language for social functional action and situational communication (Branden, Bygate & Norris, 2009). Unlike the form-based teaching approach, Task-Based Language Teaching Strategy is a meaning-based teaching approach that enables students to communicate in a meaningful way. The tasks employed in the lessons may be based on real life circumstances.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is an educational framework for the theory of teaching foreign or second languages. Breen as cited by Tekana (2014) sees task as any structure language learning endeavour which has a particular objective, appropriate content, a specified working procedural and a range of outcomes for those who undertake the task. Task is therefore assumed to refer to a range of work plans which have the overall purposes of facilitating language learning from simple and brief exercise type, to more complex and lengthy activity such as group problem solving or simulations and decision making.

From the foregoing, it can be deduced that strategy is a teaching approach which centres on solving puzzle problems, investigating topics, writing projects than on graded structures and vocabulary. It offers an alternative for language teachers hence the teacher does not pre-determine the kind of language that will be studied, but the topic is based on the completion of a central task and what is studied is determined by what happens as the learners complete the learning process.

Task-based language teaching was first developed by Prabhu in Bangalore Southern India. Prabhu in Tekena (2014) believed that students may learn more effectively when their minds are focused on task, rather than on the language they are using. Richard and Rodgers (2001) opined that using tasks for teaching first appeared in the vocational training practice of the 1950's. Task focused learning was derived from training design concerns of the military regarding new military technologies and occupational specialities of the period. Task analysis initially focused on psychomotor tasks for which little communication or collaboration was involved.

Task-based learning started in the 1970s, when scholars argued that language instructions should teach both grammar and meaning. Similarly, Richard and Rodgers, (2014) defined task as a venture carried out as the product of understanding language. It involves learners in understanding, operating, producing, or communicating in task learning while they center on caning instead of form. Task-based is an action where task learning is used by the learners for an interactive purpose in order to acquire an outcome. It emphasizes on assigning learning with a planned outcome where learners can study and perform the forms of tasks learning while paying attention to meaning. From the fore-going definitions, task-based learning is centered mainly on meaning, where the students derive meaning from the content read and less practice on the form (Willis, 2010).

Processes involved in using of task-based strategy

One of the main features of task-based learning is that the learners are free of language control rather than the language being decided by the teachers (Willis, 2010). The task-based meaning is like a language problem to solve in relation to real-world situations. A speaking task can develop students' ability to speak fluently and accurately when communicating with their peers (Nunan, 2004). In other words, in TBLT, the basic aim of second language teaching is to enable learners to use the target language for social functional action or situation in communication (Branden, Bygate & Norris, 2009). According to the different levels of the students and the different target language items, the tasks can be adapted flexibly to authentic, practical and functional uses of language for meaning.

Willis as quoted by Tekena (2014) sees a task as a goal-oriented activity which has a clear purpose and which involves achieving an outcome through creating a final product that can be appreciated by others. Breen in Tekena (2014) suggests that language tasks can be viewed as a range of work plans, from simple to complex, with the overall purpose of facilitating language learning. He sees all materials for language teaching as compendia of tasks. Such Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) is language input they receive more comprehensible, furnishing contexts in which learners need to produce output which others can understand, and finally making the classroom closer to real-life language situations.

The role of the teacher in task-based learning approach shifts away from some traditional method of the teacher roles in language teaching (Nunan, 2004). In TBLT, the teacher will decrease the proportion of the time spent on communicative processing. The main role of the teacher in TBLT is monitoring and giving feedback. The teachers are responding not only to the students' fluency, but also their accuracy. Furthermore, for large parts of the actual task, the teachers spent more time on giving background information. Task-based learning strategy is a learner-centered teaching approach (Willis, 2010). The learners' role is the main aspect during language processing. The main characteristics of the learners' role in TBLT are: the learner is a

negotiator, capable of giving as well as taking; learner is a performer and listener, with little control over the content of the learning; and the learners should take responsibility for their own learning.

Long and Crookes in Tekena (2014) have classified three different types of task-based approach. The first is the procedural task, whereby the teacher designs the procedure of the task and learners complete it. Designed tasks are more accessible for learners and more manageable by teachers than real-world tasks. The second is when the teachers and learners decide together what task to do. It is project work but connects to the real-world and distinctive enough, with special consideration of the project's world. The third type of approach is when learners engage in TBLT drawing strong attention to the language as needed. These tasks can be adapted flexibly according to the different levels of the students and the different target language items.

The process of task-based learning itself teaches important skills. Students learn how to ask questions, how to negotiate meaning and how to interact in and work within groups. Within his group work, they are able to observe different approaches to problem solving as well as to learn how others think and make decisions, these are all skills that our students will need in order to be successful in the real world, regardless of which language(s) they use there.

METHODOLOGY

The quasi-experimental design was employed. A population of ten thousand and eleven (10,011) Senior Secondary School students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was drawn for the study (Post Primary School's Board Statistics, 2022). The random sampling technique was used in selecting two schools in the area. The researchers used task-based group (TBG) and control group (CG) for the experiment. A sample size of four hundred (400) students was used from their intact classes. The instrument for data collection was a structured question tagged: "English Performance Reading Comprehension Test (EPRCT)." Face and content validity were employed to check the validity of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of the English Performance Reading Comprehension Test (EPRCT) was determined with the test-retest technique and the scores of the same sample was correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and a reliability coefficient index of 0.78 was obtained. The researcher used intact classes for the experimental group and control group in the two schools. A pretest was administered to the groups before the commencement of the teaching. The scores obtained from the result were referred to as pretest scores. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test were used to analyse the hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the difference in the pre-test performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test of Experimental and Control group

Groups	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Task-based strategy	200	13.40	2.50
Conventional lecture method	200	13.41	2.50
Total	400		

Table 1 revealed that the mean and standard deviation of task-based learning strategy group was (13.40 and 2.50), while the conventional lecture method group was (13.41 and 2.50) respectively. This showed that the students have almost the same scores in pre-test of task-based and conventional lecture method groups. There was homogeneity in the performance of the two groups at a pre-test stage.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the pre-test post-test performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategies and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test Post-test Scores of task-based learning strategy and Conventional Lecture Method Group

Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	
Task-base strategy	200	13.40	2.50	44.93	7.75	31.53
Conventional lecture method	200	13.41	2.50	34.56	6.44	21.15
Total	400					

Table 2 revealed that the mean scores and standard deviation at pre-test stage of task-base learning strategy group was (13.40 and 2.50) while that of conventional lecture method group was (13.41 and 2.50). Meanwhile, the mean score and standard deviation at post-test stage of task base learning group was (44.93 and 7.75), while that of conventional lecture method group was (34.56 and 6.44) respectively. This indicated a mean gain of (31.53 and 21.15) respectively in the pretest and post-test mean scores. This therefore showed that the students performed better in the post-test stage than the pretest stage in reading comprehension of English language.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S.

Table 3: T-test Results of Pre-test Scores of Experimental Group and Pretest of Conventional Lecture Method Group in Reading Comprehension

Group	N	Mean	Std	Df	α	T-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental group	200	13.45	2.53					
				598	0.05	0.297	0.767	Not significant
Conventional lecture method	200	13.43	2.50					

Table 3 revealed that task-based learning strategy group has a mean score of (13.45) with its corresponding standard deviation of (2.53), while conventional lecture method group has mean score of (13.43) with its corresponding standard deviation of (2.56). Again, the independent T-test also shows that calculated t- value of 0.297 and P- value of 0.767 > 0.05 (which is greater than) the chosen level of significant at 598 degree of freedom was obtained. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, while the alternate hypothesis is rejected. This implied that there is no significant difference in the pretest scores of task-based learning strategy group and conventional lecture method group in of reading comprehension in English language, hence $p > 0.05$, the alpha level.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the pretest posttest performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method in Obio/Akpor LGA, R/S.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results of Pre-test Post-test Scores of Students in Experimental Group and Conventional lecture method group in Reading Comprehension

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Alpha level	F-value	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	22114.626	2	11057.313		219.873	.000	Significant
Intercept	31915.827	1	31915.827	0.05	634.641	.000	
Pretest	38.285	1	38.285		.761	.000	
Group	22095.423	1	22095.423		439.364	.000	
Error	30022.893	597	50.290				
Total	1168687.000	600					

Table 4 of the ANCOVA results revealed F-value of 439.36 and P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant at 597 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, hence the $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ the alpha level. This indicated that there is significant difference in the pretest post-test performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using task-based learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method.

Discussion of Findings

Difference in the pretest mean scores of students taught with the task-based strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method group in reading comprehension

The result of table 1 revealed that the mean scores for experimental group was (13.45), while that of control group was (13.43). This indicated that the students have almost the same scores at the pretest scores of task-based learning strategy groups and conventional lecture method group. The students also have equal ability in their performance in the groups before the treatment. Again, the independent t-test results indicated ($t = 0.297, P = 0.767 > 0.05$) which is greater than the chosen level of significant at 598 degree of freedom. This therefore implies that there is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of experimental group and control group. It also indicated that the null hypothesis is not rejected. This is because the students have homogeneity scores and also treatment has not taken place in the experimental group at pretest stages. This study is in agreement with that study of Anunaobi and Inko-tariah (2020) who found that there is no significant difference in the pretest of both experimental and control group of their own studies. They also noted that student's intellectual capability also plays a great part in their positive development.

Difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores of students taught with task-based and those taught with the conventional lecture method group in reading comprehension

Table 2 revealed that the mean scores at pre-test stage of task-based learning group was (13.40) while that of conventional lecture method group was (13.41). Meanwhile, the mean scores at post-test stage of task base learning strategy were (44.93) while that of conventional lecture method group was (34.56) respectively. This indicated a mean difference of (31.53) between task-based and conventional group and (21.15) in the pretest and post-test of conventional group. This therefore showed that students performed better in the post-test stage than the pretest stage in of reading comprehension in English Language. Again, as shown in table 4.4, the computed ANCOVA results produce $F = 439.364, df (1, 597) P = 0.000 < 0.05$ the chosen level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the pre-test scores and post-test scores of students in experimental groups and conventional lecture method group was rejected.

The result showed that students performed better at the post-test stage than the pretest stage in the favour of the experimental groups than the conventional lecture method group because of the treatment. This study is in line with the study of Tekena (2014), who found difference in the pretest and post-test scores of experimental and control groups on effect of motivation and grammatical achievement of junior high school students. His results revealed that there is significant difference in the pre-test scores and post-test scores of students in experimental and control groups. He contributed that there is always a positive result when students share ideas, skill, knowledge and experience with others. The experiment conducted by Slavin collaborating Anunaobi and Inko-Tariah (2020) revealed that there is difference in pre-test and post-test of experimental groups and control group based on co-operative and task-based in reading of comprehension in English language of secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

The task-based strategy enhances interaction, communication and practical work amongst students and on the side of teachers as guides, facilitators and motivators and stresses the autonomy and centrality of the students in the classroom. From the fore-going, it is advocated in this work that task-based methods of teaching reading should be encouraged in order to provide a better understand and greater performance in reading in reading comprehension rather than sticking to teaching of reading through discussion learning method. Student to student interaction is rare, since the mindset of teachers is seen only as students acquiring knowledge from them and not from their fellow students.

Base on the findings, task-based learning strategy serves as a motivating factor for students to do meaningful task or activities using target plans to achieve a good result in reading comprehension in English language. Individual interest and concentration in English language subject classes yielded greater effect in reading comprehension of female students than male students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the research, the following recommendations were made;

1. Task-based learning strategy should be introduced in teaching of reading comprehension in secondary schools.
2. Ministry of education should encourage teacher in the use of innovative strategies in order to bring about good result in student's reading abilities.

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